

Leucoanthocyanidins and Related Compounds*

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To-day is the birth-anniversary of the late Dr. Basudev Banerjee in whose memory the Basudev Banerjee medal and prize are instituted. On behalf of myself and my research colleagues I pay homage to the memory of the late Dr. Basudev Banerjee. I am indeed grateful to the Council of the Indian Chemical Society for the award of the prize to me and calling upon me to deliver the second Basudev Banerjee Memorial Lecture.

According to the conditions of award the lecture is to be based on the research work carried out during the last five years. Instead of giving diffuse and sketchy information on different topics I was interested in, during this period, I have confined myself to leucoanthocyanidins, which have recently aroused a great interest all over the World, and to which field my laboratory has made a substantial contribution.

Leucoanthocyanidins, their Occurrence in Nature and Importance

Anthocyanins, which are responsible for the red, violet, and blue pigmentations of flowers and many fruits, are derivatives of 2-benzopyrylium chloride (Ia). They give aglycones called, anthocyanidins (Ib) on hydrolysis with mineral acids. During the investigation of the young leaves of grape vine, Rosenheim¹ isolated a colorless substance, which yielded anthocyanidin on boiling with hydrochloric acid and called it as "leucoanthocyanin"². He suggested that such compounds were glycosides (III) of the pseudobases (II) of the corresponding anthocyanidins.

Cyanidin chloride. Ia: R=glucosyl. Ib: R=H, Cyanin pseudobase. R=glycosyl, H.

Taking into consideration their relationship with anthocyanidins, they³ preferred the term "leucoanthocyanidins" and proposed the structure (IV) for them. Later investigations on leucoanthocyanins led Robinson⁴ to believe that these have the state of oxidation of dihydroanthocyanidins and hence are flavan-3,4-diols (V) rather than flavan-2,3,4-triols (IV).

The isolation by King and Bottomley^{5,6} of a naturally occurring flavan-3,4-diol-melaca-

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cidin (VI) and its analogous behaviour towards mineral acids; the studies of Bauer, Birch, and Hillis⁷ on the reduction products of acetates of quercetin and aromadendrin indeed support the hypothesis of Robinson; now it may be safely concluded that the natural leucoanthocyanidins have a flavan-3,4-diol structure.

(VI)
A flavan-3,4-diol.

(V)
Melacacidin.

Leucoanthocyanins play a possible role in the biogenesis of flavonoid compounds. Robinson^{2,4} suggested that the transformation of leucoanthocyanins into the colouring matters of the flavylum type might be occurring in nature. This concept that leucoanthocyanins are the immediate precursors of anthocyanins and flavonols, has been recently supported by several workers⁵⁻¹⁷. Two other interesting functions of leucoanthocyanins may be mentioned. Masquelier and Tayaeu¹⁸ have shown that the peanut leucoanthocyanin has vitamin-P activity and Audus¹⁹ has reported stimulation of cell division by leucoanthocyanins.

Robinson and Robinson² first showed the wide distribution of leucoanthocyanins in the plant kingdom. Bate-Smith and co-workers²⁰⁻²⁵, however, pointed out that these were confined mainly to woody plants, and speculated a close structural relationship between leucoanthocyanins and the condensed tannins. This speculation has been amply supported during the last seven years and as many as eight representatives of this class of compounds have been isolated in crystalline form mostly from tannin-bearing plants. Melacacidin (VII) was discovered in *Acacia melanoxylon* by King and Bottomley²⁶. Mollisacacidin (VIII) was isolated by Keppler²⁶ from *Acacia mollissima* and its enantiomorph was found in the quebracho wood by Freudenberg and co-workers²⁷⁻²⁹. This was followed by the isolation of leucorobinetidin (IX) by Weinges³⁰ from *Robinia pseudacacia*. Seshadri and co-workers³¹⁻³³ reported the occurrence of leucoacyanidin (X) in *Butea frondosa*, leucopelargonidin (XI) in *Eucalyptus calophylla* gum, and leucodelphinidin (XII) in *Cleistanthus collinus*. Very recently, presence of guibourtacacidin (XIII) in the species of genus *Guibourtia* by Roux³⁴ and teracacidin (XIV) in *Acacia intertexta* by Clark-Lewis and Mortimer³⁵ is reported.

(VII)
7,3,3',4'-Tetrahydroxyflavan-3,4-diol
(Melacacidin).

(VIII)
7,3',4'-Trihydroxyflavan-3,4-diol
(Mollisacacidin).

(IX)
7,3',4',5'-Tetrahydroxyflavan-3,4-diol
(Leucorobinetidin).

(X)
5,7,3',4'-Tetrahydroxyflavan-3,4-diol
(Leucoacyanidin).

(XI)

5,7,4',-Trihydroxyflavan-3,4-diol
(Leucopelargonidin).

(XII)

5,7,3',4',5'-Pentahydroxyflavan-3,4-diol
(Leucodelphinidin).

(XIII)

7,4'-Dihydroxyflavan-3,4-diol
(Guibourtaecidin).

(XIV)

7,8,4'-Trihydroxyflavan-3,4-diol
(Teracacidin).

Until recently, very little was known about the structure of phlobatannins. In early twenties, Freudenberg³⁶ put forth his catechin hypothesis and stated that phlobatannins were the polymers of catechins. The following probable course of polymerisation with acidic reagents was suggested³⁷⁻³⁸. The present knowledge shows that catechins may be the building units of only a group of phlobatannins, which are present in Burma cutch or gambier extracts³⁹.

(XV)

Catechin.

(XVI)

Dicatechin.

Like catechins, flavan-3,4-diols, themselves have no tanning properties; they are, however, polymerised with mineral acids to give soluble tannins and insoluble phlobaphenes⁴⁰⁻⁴¹. Sufficient experimental evidence has been recently put forth by Roux⁴²⁻⁴³ to show that this process of polymerisation takes place in the wood and monomeric leucoanthocyanidins

(XVII)

Leucoanthocyanidin.

(XVIII)

Dileucoanthocyanidin.

are converted into complex polymeric ones, which have tanning properties. Thus flavan-3,4-diols are the building units of at least a group of phlobatannins, which occur in wattle and quebracho wood⁴⁴. A probable course of self-condensation⁴¹ is indicated as shown above.

The above short review shows that leucoanthocyanidins are important as they themselves occur in nature, are the building units of phlobatannins, and play a significant role in the biogenesis of flavonoid pigments. Very little synthetic work has been reported in the field and hence studies in that direction are essential. The problem of synthesis of flavan-3,4-diols is exciting and complicated because of the three asymmetric centres present in the molecule. Four racemates or eight optically active isomers of an individual flavan-3,4-diol are theoretically possible and are likely to occur in nature. An elaborate programme of research on different aspects of leucoanthocyanidins was therefore undertaken with my colleagues at the National Chemical Laboratories, Poona and the Institute of Science, Bombay. Methods for their synthesis were evolved, their stereochemistry was established, and a few naturally occurring ones were synthesised.

Synthesis of the Four Racemates of 6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3,4-diol

Preliminary investigations on the reduction of anthoxanthins, such as, 1,2,6,8-tetramethoxyxanthone (XIX), 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavone (XX), 6-methyl-3,4'-dimethoxyflavone (XXI), and 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone (XXII), with lithium aluminium hydride were carried out with a view to studying the course of reduction and to establishing the optimum experimental conditions. The corresponding xanthene⁴⁵ (XXIII),

flavene⁴⁶ (XXIV), 3-methoxyflav-2-ene⁴⁷ (XXV), and flavan-4-ol⁴⁷ (XXVI) were obtained respectively. In the case of reduction of the flavanone, only one isomer could be obtained though theoretically two can exist.

The First Two Racemates.—Thus it has been established that metal hydrides are convenient reducing agents for anthoxanthins. It was thought that the dihydroflavonols would serve as intermediates and would give the desired leucoanthocyanidins on reduction with these reagents. When these investigations were undertaken in 1954, a survey of the literature showed that only an isolated example of synthetic flavan-3, 4-diol, i.e., the unsubstituted one⁴⁸ was known. 6-Methyl-4'-methoxydihydroflavonol (XXVII) was therefore reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and the corresponding two flavan-3, 4-diols^{49,50} (XXVIII and XXIX), isomeric in position '4', were isolated. Almost simultaneously, publications from Freudenberg and Roux⁵¹, King and Clark-Lewis⁵²⁻⁵³, and Swain⁵⁴ appeared wherein they reported the synthesis of flavandiols. Only one racemate in each case was, however, reported by these workers.

The Third Racemate.—Having accomplished the synthesis of the first two racemates, we directed our attention to the synthesis of the remaining two racemates. The obvious choice of the starting material would be the corresponding isomeric dihydroflavonol having a different configuration for the C₃-OH. We were therefore dragged into the field of dihydroflavonols—different methods for their synthesis and their stereochemistry. These investigations form a separate chapter in itself and are discussed in the later part of the lecture. It is relevant to note here that the isomeric dihydroflavonol could not be synthesised^{55,56} and the approach had to be reluctantly abandoned. Attempts to use the flav-3-ene as an intermediate for the synthesis of a flavan-3, 4-diol through the following sequence of reactions also failed⁵⁷.

At this stage of the investigation a stray observation of Limaye⁵⁸ that 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanone exists in two isomeric forms, became useful to us. Both these isomers of 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanone were synthesised and their isomerism in position '3' was proved⁵⁹ by the fact that on debromination both gave the same corresponding flavone. Replacement of bromine of both the compounds by a hydroxy or an acetoxy group and synthesis of the isomeric dihydroflavonols could not be realised as

dehydrobromination to the corresponding flavone occurred⁵⁵. This difficulty was circumvented by first reducing the bromoflavanones to the bromohydrins with lithium aluminium hydride. 6-Methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanone (XXX) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to the bromohydrin (XXXI) and bromine was replaced by a hydroxy group by boiling the bromohydrin with alkali in dioxan⁵⁹. Thus the third racemate of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3,4-diol was synthesised. Its diacetate (XXXII) could be obtained in a crystalline form from the diol by acetylation or directly by treating the bromohydrin with anhydrous potassium acetate. Repetition of the experimental conditions on the isomeric 3-bromoflavanone (XXXIII) gave the bromohydrin (XXXIV); replacement of bromine by a hydroxy or an acetoxy group was, however, unsuccessful and resulted, presumably, in the formation of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflav-3-ene-4-acetate⁵⁹ (XXXV). Attempts to prepare the flavan-3,4-epoxide from this bromohydrin with a view to opening it stereospecifically to the flavan-3,4-diol also failed⁵⁹.

The Fourth Racemate.—By this time, stereochemical investigations on flavan-3,4-diols in our laboratory and elsewhere were sufficiently advanced to give us a clue that the fourth racemate of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3,4-diol could be synthesised by catalytic hydrogenation of the corresponding flavonol. 6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavonol (XXXVI) was hydrogenated over Raney nickel at high temperature and pressure, and, indeed, the corresponding flavan-3,4-diol (XXXVII), the fourth racemate, was obtained^{56,60}.

Stereochemistry of Leucoanthocyanidins

The above synthetic work on leucoanthocyanidins would not be complete unless their stereochemistry was established. As very little stereochemical data on the intermediate compounds, such as, dihydroflavonols, bromoflavanones, and bromohydrins, were known, detailed stereochemical investigations on these compounds were carried out and the stereochemistry of leucoanthocyanidins was settled.

Stereochemistry of Dihydroflavonols.—A dihydroflavonol contains two asymmetric centres and hence can exist in two racemic forms. We were the first to introduce Barton's concept of conformational analysis⁶¹ in this field to elucidate its stereochemistry⁶². The dihydropyran ring was compared with cyclohexene⁶³ and the bulky side phenyl nucleus was assigned an equatorial conformation^{55,62}. On the basis of dehydrogenation data⁵⁵ on some of the dihydroflavonols, synthesised in our laboratory, along with that put forth by Seshadri and co-workers⁶⁴ on natural and synthetic 3-hydroxynaringenin, an equatorial conformation for C₃-OH of the synthetic dihydroflavonols was proposed. Thus a working hypothesis⁵⁵ has been put forward that C₂-phenyl and C₃-OH of the synthetic dihydroflavonols, which are dehydrogenated, are *trans*-oriented. The dehydration between C₂-H and C₃-OH of 3-hydroxynaringenin, which was prepared by a replacement reaction, was explained⁵⁵ on the basis of *trans*-(a, a) elimination principle⁶¹. It was therefore assigned a *cis*-configuration [C₂-Ph(e), C₃-OH(a)]. Seshadri and co-workers⁶⁵ arrived at the same conclusions regarding the stereochemistry of dihydroflavonols.

It became necessary to prove to which series the dihydroflavonols synthesised by different methods belonged and, if possible, to prepare an epimeric dihydroflavonol with C₃-OH(a) so that it might serve as an intermediate for the synthesis of the third and the fourth race-

mates. All the methods for the synthesis of dihydroflavonols were therefore worked out in our laboratory; the identical dihydroflavonols were synthesised by two different methods and thus the various methods were correlated. An epimeric ($\pm$)-6-methyl-4'-methoxy-dihydroflavonol, required for the synthesis of the third and the fourth racemate, could not be synthesised by any of the known methods. The established co-ordination among the methods of synthesis and the dehydrogenation data on the dihydroflavonols enabled us, however, to assign conformations to both the synthetic and natural dihydroflavonols. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE I
Conformations of synthetic and natural dihydroflavonols⁵⁵.

Dihydroflavonol.	Nature.	Dehydrogenation or dehydra- tion with H ₂ SO ₄ .	Conformation for C ₃ -OH.
1st Series:			
1. 6-Methyl-4'-methoxy	Synthetic	Dehydrogenation	e
2. 7,4'-Dimethoxy	"	Not known	e
3. 7,8,3',4'-Tetramethoxy	"	Dehydrogenation	e
4. 6-Benzoyl-4'-methoxy	"	Not known	e
5. Fustin trimethyl ether	"	"	e
6. Taxifolin	Natural	Dehydrogenation	e
7. Dihydrorobinetin	"	"	e
8. 3-Hydroxynaringenin	"	"	e
9. Alpinone	"	Not known	e
"	Synthetic		
10. Pinobanksin	Natural conver- ted to alpinone	No dehydrogenation (?)	e
2nd Series:			
11. 3-Hydroxynaringenin	Synthetic	Dehydration	a
12. 3-Hydroxyhesperitin	"	Not known	a

As the table reveals, we proposed that the naturally occurring dihydroflavonols belong to the *trans*-series⁵⁵. The validity of this hypothesis, that the naturally occurring dihydroflavonols are *trans* compounds, is established beyond doubt by later publications of Freudenberg and Weinges⁵⁹ and Clark-Lewis and co-workers⁶⁶. Thus ($\pm$)-dihydroquercetin tetramethyl ether was converted by hydrogenation over platinum catalyst to ($\pm$)-catechin tetramethyl ether⁶⁷, the stereochemistry of which as 2,3-*trans*-compound is well established.

Stereochemistry of the First Two Racemates.—Thus the synthetic 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-dihydroflavonol (XLII) was assigned a *trans*-configuration [C₂-Ph(e); C₃-OH(e)] and hence the stereochemistry of the first two racemates of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3,4-diol could be deduced. On the basis of the generalisation⁶¹ that catalytic hydrogenation of an unhindered ketone in an acidic medium affords an axial alcohol, C₄-OH of the lower melting racemate was assigned an axial conformation. It followed that C₄-OH of the other isomer was equatorial. Thus the lower melting racemate (XLIII) was assigned 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*cis*-configuration [C₂-Ph(e), C₃-OH(e), C₄-OH(a)] and the higher melting isomer (XLIV) 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*trans*-configuration⁶²⁻⁶⁸ [C₂-Ph(e), C₃-OH(e), C₄-OH(e)]. The assignments postulated comply with Auwer-Skita rule⁶⁹ and are further supported by the fact that only the isomer having 3,4-*cis*-configuration [C₃-OH(e), C₄-OH(a)] forms a cyclic carbonate⁶⁸ (XLV). The sequence of chromatographic elution⁶⁸ and velocity of hydrolysis⁶⁸ of the diol diacetates are also in agreement with the configurations assigned.

On the basis of these investigations, stereochemical configurations were assigned to synthetic leucoanthocyanidins, such as allo- and isallo-melacacidin tetramethyl ether⁶², mollisacacidin trimethyl ether⁷⁰, guibourtacacidin dimethyl ether⁷¹, allo-, and isallo-teracacidin trimethyl ether⁷², all of which have been proved to be true by independent stereochemical investigations from other laboratories^{35,53,73}.

Stereochemistry of 3-Bromoflavanones

Stereochemistry of 3-bromoflavanones and the corresponding bromohydrins needed to be first established so that the stereochemical pattern for the third racemate could be evolved. Limaye⁷⁴ reported the conversion of the isomer (m.p. 138°) into its epimer (m.p. 167°) by boiling it with acetic acid-hydrochloric acid. The latter could not be converted into the former⁷⁴. These facts led us to propose that the stable isomer (m.p. 167°) possessed a favoured (2,3-*trans*) configuration and its epimer (m.p. 138°), 2,3-*cis*-configuration⁶⁸. I.R. spectroscopic studies of α -halogeno-cyclic ketones have helped to assign conformation to halogen atoms⁷⁵. A band of lower frequency (663 cm^{-1}) in the infrared curve of the lower melting isomer indicated $\text{C}_3\text{-Br}$ axial and a band of higher frequency (752 cm^{-1}) in the curve of its isomer⁶⁸ showed it to be equatorial⁷⁶. This physical evidence is in agreement with the configurations suggested earlier⁶⁸ for the isomeric 3-bromoflavanones. These were finally confirmed by the chemical evidence, *i.e.*, studying velocity of dehydrobromination⁷⁷ of both the isomers. On the basis of a, *a-trans* elimination principle, the isomer with $\text{C}_2\text{-H(a)}$, $\text{C}_3\text{-Br(a)}$ would be dehydrobrominated faster than the one with $\text{C}_2\text{-H(a)}$, $\text{C}_3\text{-Br(e)}$. The velocity of dehydrobromination of both the isomers measured U.V. spectroscopically noting the intensity of absorption at the maximum $3200\text{\AA}$ of the

flavone formed, indeed proved that it was so. Thus, this novel kinetic approach confirmed the assignments, *i.e.*, the lower melting isomer (XLVI) has 2,3-*cis*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -Br(a)], whereas the higher melting isomer (XLVII) has 2,3-*trans*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -Br(e)].

FIG. 1. Dehydrobromination of (A) 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavone (m.p. 167°) and (B) 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavone (m.p. 138°).

Stereochemistry of the Bromohydrins

C_4 -OH of the isomeric bromohydrins can be either equatorial or axial. Its conformation in both of them was settled⁷⁷ by reductively debrominating them with lithium aluminium hydride and isolating the identical flavan-4-ol (LIV), which was previously synthesised by hydrogenating the flavanone over platinum catalyst in an acidic medium. Thus the bromohydrin (XLIX) (m.p. 200°) was assigned 2,3-*cis*-3,4-*trans*-configuration [(C_2 -PH(e), C_3 -Br(a), C_4 -OH(a))] and the other bromohydrin (L) (m.p. 175°) was assigned 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*cis*-configuration⁷⁷ [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -Br(e), C_4 -OH(a)]. Here it may be pointed out that the use of lithium aluminium hydride, which is sometimes known to debrominate through an epoxide formation⁷⁸, does not introduce any doubt in the above stereochemical conclusion since such a mechanism could only affect the C_3 -Br bond and not the C_4 -OH bond.

Stereochemistry of the Third Racemate

The diacetate (LIII) of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3,4-diol, synthesised from the bromohydrin, with 2,3-*cis*-3,4-*trans*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -Br(a), C_4 -OH(a)] by treatment with potassium acetate in alcohol is different from the diacetates of the first two racemates, which are isomeric in position '4'. It follows by exclusion that this racemate must have a different configuration, *i.e.*, C_3 -OCOCH₃ must be axial. Taking into consideration the

axial conformation of C_4 -OH of the bromohydrin, it was therefore assigned 2,3-*cis*-3,4-*trans*-configuration⁶⁸ [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OCOCH₃(a), C_4 -OCOCH₃(a)]. Further, on treatment with sodium hydroxide in dioxane, the 3-bromoflavan-4-ol (XLIX) gave an epoxide⁶⁸ (LI), which on opening with acetic acid-sulphuric acid and acetylation gave the same diol diacetate (LIII). This may be explained on the basis of the accepted mechanism of the formation of an epoxide with inversion at the C_3 -Br bond⁷⁹, *i.e.*, C_3 -Br(a) $\rightarrow$ C_3 -O(e) and its *trans*-a, a-opening^{80,83}. Thus the diol diacetate should have both C_3 -OCOCH₃ and C_4 -OCOCH₃ axial. Inversion at C_3 -Br, *i.e.*, C_3 -Br(a) $\rightarrow$ C_3 -O(e), assumed to take place during the formation of the epoxide, does not militate the explanation given above for the retention of configuration as it is well established by Weinstein⁸⁴ and Shoppee⁸⁵ that the solvent and the reagent play a very important part in deciding the halogen replacement mechanism.

Stereochemistry of the Fourth Racemate

The remaining fourth racemate (LVI) would have 2,3-*cis*-3,4-*cis*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(a), C_4 -OH(e)], the same as assigned to the synthetic melacacidin derivative by King and Clark-Lewis⁹³. This assignment of these authors is complementary to our above assignments to the three racemates and is in agreement with both the formation of cyclic carbonate from their diol and the generalisation of catalytic *cis*-addition of hydrogen to the double bond of the flavonol and formation of the comparatively stable isomer.

Thus these complicated synthetic and stereochemical investigations extending over six

years were brought to a successful conclusion and a substantial contribution to the stereochemistry of flavans, which was so little known in 1954 (with the exception of catechins) when these investigations were undertaken, was made.

Synthesis of Naturally Occurring Dihydroflavonols

In connection with the work on flavan-3,4-diols, the method of Limaye⁸⁶ for the synthesis of dihydroflavonols was well standardised. This was extended and the naturally occurring dihydroflavonols—fustin and dihydrorobinetin—were synthesised⁸⁷ as their trimethyl ether and tetramethyl ether, respectively. The chalcone acetate was converted through its dibromide to the corresponding dihydroflavonol (LXXIV) by boiling with aqueous acetone-sodium carbonate and thus fustin trimethyl ether was obtained. Similarly 2'-acetoxy-4', 2,4,5-tetramethoxychalcone was brominated and the dibromide was cyclised with aqueous acetone-sodium carbonate to dihydrorobinetin tetramethyl ether (LXIX). The synthetic sample showed no depression in a mixed melting point determination with the tetramethyl ether of the natural dihydrorobinetin, kindly supplied by Prof. Freudenberg⁸⁸.

Synthesis of Naturally Occurring Leucoanthocyanidins or their Epimers

Once the methods for the synthesis of leucoanthocyanidins were evolved, we directed our attention to the syntheses of naturally occurring ones.

Melacacidin.—King and co-workers⁵⁶ isolated the first leucoanthocyanidin, melacacidin, as its tetramethyl ether in a crystalline form. The following sequence of reactions to achieve its synthesis gave us its epimers^{56-6a}.

2'-Acetoxy-3',4',3,4-tetramethoxychalkone was converted through its dibromide (LVII) to the corresponding dihydroflavonol (LVIII). The latter was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to a colorless flavan-3,4-diol (LIX). When the dihydroflavonol (LVIII) was hydrogenated over platinum catalyst in acetic acid, the other racemate (LX) was obtained. From models and geometrical considerations, the first racemate (LIX) was assigned 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*trans*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(e), C_4 -OH(e)] and the second one (LX) 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*cis*-configuration⁵⁵ [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(e), C_4 -OH(a)]. Later investigators⁵³, as discussed above, confirmed these stereochemical assignments. The racemates can now be designated as alloiso- and allo-melacacidin derivatives, respectively.

Teracacidin.—Clark-Lewis and Mortimer⁵⁵ recently reported the isolation of new leucoanthocyanidins, teracacidin and isoteracacidin, from *Acacia intertexta*. They have further shown that teracacidin has 7,8,4'-trihydroxyflavan-3,4-diol structure and is stereochemically analogous to melacacidin, *i.e.*, it has 2,3-*cis*-3,4-*cis*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(a), C_4 -OH(e)] and isoteracacidin is its epimer and has 2,3-*cis*-3,4-*trans*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(a), C_4 -OH(a)]. 7,8,4'-Trimethoxydihydroflavonol (LXII) was prepared by cyclisation of the corresponding acetoxychalkone dibromide (LXI) by the Raschig reaction⁵⁶ and its acetate (LXIII) was reduced with hydrogen over Raney nickel when the corresponding leucoanthocyanidin monoacetate (LXIV) was obtained. On hydrolysis, the flavan-3,4-diol (LXV) could be isolated⁷². The dihydroflavonol (LXVI) on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride gave a mixture of isomeric flavan-3,4-diols, which was difficult

to separate. On several crystallisations the other racemate (LXVIII) could be isolated²¹. The flavan-3,4-diols (LXVII) and (LXVIII) have been assigned 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*cis*-[C₂-Ph(e), C₃-OH(e), C₄-OH(a)] and 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*trans*-configurations [C₂-Ph(e), C₃OH(e), C₄-OH(e)] and have been called as allo- and alloiso-teracacidin, respectively.

Leucorobinetinidin.—Synthesis of the naturally occurring dihydroflavonol, dihydro-robinetin, as its tetramethyl ether (LXIX) has already been described above. It was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride, when a mixture of two compounds was obtained. On several crystallisations the pure leucoanthocyanidin (LXX) could be isolated²⁰. Its stereo-

specific synthesis could be achieved by hydrogenating the dihydroflavonol over platinum black in acetic acid. From the method of synthesis, it follows that it has 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*cis*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(e), C_4 -OH(a)] and in all probability belongs to the same stereochemical series as that of (-)-leucorobinetinidin, recently isolated by Weinges⁹⁰.

Guibourtacacidin.—Roux³⁴ indicated the presence of a new leucoanthocyanidin, "Guibourtacacidin", in the species of genus *Guibourtia* and suggested it to be 7,4'-dihydroxyflavan-3,4-diol. We extended our method for its synthesis as the dimethyl ether. 7,4'-Dimethoxydihydroflavonol (LXXI) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and the mixture of isomeric flavan-3,4-diols was conveniently separated by acetylating it and fractionally crystallising the diacetates. The diacetate of diol (LXXII) separated at first. On hydrolysis the corresponding diol (LXXII) could be obtained⁷¹. The mother liquor of crystallisation of the acetates was then hydrolysed and the second diol (LXXIII) was isolated⁷¹. The first (LXXII) of these isomeric diols could be obtained in a quantitative yield on reduction of the dihydroflavonol (LXXI) with sodium borohydride. On the basis of stereospecificity of reducing agents and our hypothesis regarding the stereochemical configurations of flavan-3,4-diols, the diol (LXXII) was assigned 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*cis*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(e), C_4 -OH(a)] and is almost certainly identical with the dimethyl ether of the natural guibourtacacidin⁷¹. The other diol (LXXIII) would then have 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*trans*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(e), C_4 -OH(e)].

Mollisacacidin.—Keppler⁴⁶ isolated ($\pm$)-mollisacacidin from *Acacia mollissima* and assigned to it 7,3',4'-trihydroxyflavan-3,4-diol structure. Its identity with gleditsin, isolated from *Gleditsia japonica* (Miquel) by Mitsuno and Yushizaki⁹⁰, was established by Clark-Lewis and Mitsuno⁹¹. Recently (-)-leucosifetinidin was isolated from quebracho wood by

Freudenberg and co-workers²⁷⁻²⁹ and was shown to be enantiomorphous with ($\pm$)-mollisacacidin. The latter was partially synthesised by Keppler²⁶ by hydrogenation of fustin, obtained from *Rhus glabra*. Simultaneously, Chandorkar and Kulkarni⁷⁰ prepared ($\pm$)-fustin trimethyl ether (LXXIV), reduced it with lithium aluminium hydride, isolated two isomers (LXXV and LXXVI) of 7,3',4'-trimethoxyflavan-3,4-diol, and assigned to one of them (LXXV) a 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*cis*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(e), C_4 -OH(a)] and suggested its possible identity with the corresponding ($\pm$)-mollisacacidin derivative. Clark-Lewis and Roux⁷⁹ confirmed this suggestion by a mixed melting point determination and infrared measurements on the diacetates.

The above leucoanthocyanidins were synthesised as their methyl ethers, whereas in nature they occur as phenols. Synthesis of leucoanthocyanidins with free phenolic hydroxy groups was therefore undertaken. So far synthetic crystalline leucoanthocyanidins have been obtained by hydrogenation of the naturally occurring dihydroflavonols^{26, 29, 31, 32, 42}. Synthesis of ($\pm$)-mollisacacidin (LXXX), reported by us⁹³, therefore forms the first total synthesis of a crystalline ($\pm$) leucoanthocyanidin with free phenolic hydroxy groups. 2'-Acetoxy-4',3,4-tribenzyloxychalkone dibromide (LXXVII) was cyclised to the corresponding dihydroflavonol (LXXVIII). It was reduced with sodium borohydride when the *cis*-diol was obtained in a quantitative yield. 7,3',4'-Tribenzyloxyflavan-3,4-diol (LXXIX), thus obtained, was smoothly converted into ($\pm$)-mollisacacidin (LXXX) by dissolving it in dimethyl formamide and debenzylating it by hydrogen over Pd/C. It was crystallised from luke warm water. This diol would have 2,3-*trans*-3,4-*cis*-configuration [C_2 -Ph(e), C_3 -OH(e), C_4 -OH(a)] and hence belong to the same stereochemical series as the naturally occurring mollisacacidin. The identity of this synthetic ($\pm$)-mollisacacidin with the racemate prepared from the naturally occurring enantiomorphs of mollisacacidin was established by Clark-Lewis (private communication) by mixed melting point and infrared determinations. We are grateful to him for the same.

A New Method for the Synthesis of-Catechins

Lastly I would like to deal with an interesting offshoot of the above investigations, *i.e.*, a novel method evolved in our laboratory for the synthesis of isomeric catechins. 3-Hydroxyflavans or catechins have been extensively studied for the last thirty years by Freudenberg and his school. 3,5,7,3',4'-Pentahydroxyflavan was isolated in all the possible four optically active and two racemic forms⁹⁴. It is now conclusively proved that (+)-catechin is the *trans*-isomer and (-)-epicatechin, the *cis*-one⁹⁵⁻⁹⁷. Birch and co-workers⁹⁸ used the elegant atrolactic acid method of Prelog and co-workers⁹⁹ and assigned absolute configurations to (+)-catechin and (-)-epicatechin.

Synthetic catechins are generally prepared by hydrogenation of flavonols¹⁰⁰ or flavylum salts^{95,101}. Only one racemate belonging to the epicatechin series is obtained in each case though theoretically two can exist. (+)-Catechin could be epimerised to (+)-epicatechin⁹⁴ and (-)-epicatechin to (-)-catechin⁹⁴. A method for the direct synthesis of a racemate belonging to the catechin series was, however, until recently unknown. Freudenberg and co-workers^{29,30} obtained *trans*-catechins by hydrogenolysis of the naturally occurring dihydroflavonols. The latter method is obviously of a limited applicability.

Kashikar and Kulkarni⁵⁶ reported for the first time the synthesis of both the possible racemates of 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-hydroxyflavan. One of the racemates (LXXXII) belonging to the epicatechin series was obtained by hydrogenation of the corresponding flavonol (LXXXI), whereas the other racemate (LXXXIV) was synthesised by reduction of the flavonol benzoate (LXXXIII) with lithium aluminium hydride and subsequent hydrogenation of the complex *in situ* over Raney nickel. It was later on found that instead of the flavonol benzoate (LXXXIII), if the benzylether (LXXXV) was used for the reduction, the yield of the isomer could be improved¹⁰². In this procedure a two-stage reduction of the flavonol benzylether is involved. Theoretically, such a reduction may lead to the formation of either a 4-hydroxyflavan or a 3-hydroxyflavan. That the new diastereoisomer is a 3-hydroxyflavan has been proved by the isolation of an intermediate, 7,3',4'-trimethoxy-3-benzyloxyflavan (LXXXVIII), from the corresponding flavonol benzylether (LXXXVII) in the synthesis of (+)-fisetinidol trimethyl ether (LXXXVI) and its conversion to the same catechin¹⁰³. On treatment with phosphorus pentachloride, 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-hydroxyflavan (LXXXIV), prepared by this method, gave the corresponding 2-chloroisoflavan¹⁰² (LXXXVI), characteristic of a *trans*-catechin¹⁰³. This stereochemical

assignment was further confirmed by a lowering in mixed melting point of ($\pm$)-afzelechin trimethyl ether [($\pm$)-*trans*-5,7,4'-trimethoxy-3-hydroxyflavan¹⁰²] (XCI), synthesised by the above method with (-)-epiafzelechin trimethyl ether [($-$)-*cis*-5,7,4'-trimethoxy-3-hydroxyflavan], kindly sent by Prof. King⁹⁵. The above stereochemical assignments to the catechins are tentative and their confirmation by I. R. data is awaited.

(LXXXI)
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavonol.

(LXXXII)
cis-6-Methyl-4'-methoxy-3-hydroxyflavan.

(LXXXIII)
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavonol benzoate.

(LXXXIV)
trans-6-Methyl-4'-methoxy-3-hydroxyflavan.

(LXXXV)
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavonol benzyl ether.

(LXXXVI)
6-Methyl-4'-methoxy-3-chloroisoflavan.

Synthesis of ($\pm$)-Fisetinidol Trimethyl Ether, ($\pm$)-Robinetinidol Tetramethyl Ether and ($\pm$)-Afzelechin Trimethyl Ether.

This new method was then extended to the synthesis of the naturally occurring catechins. 7,3',4'-Trimethoxyflavonol benzyl ether (LXXXVII) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride, the complex *in situ* was hydrogenated over Raney nickel, and the corresponding 3-benzyloxyflavan (LXXXVIII) was isolated. It was further debenzylated with hydrogen over Raney nickel to ($\pm$)-fisetinidol trimethyl ether¹⁰² (LXXXIX). Similarly 7,3',4',5'-Tetramethoxyflavonol benzyl ether (XC) under the above experimental conditions gave the corresponding 3-hydroxyflavan (XCI), i.e. ($\pm$)-robinetinidol tetramethyl ether. A considerable time was spent in preparing 5,7,4'-trimethoxyflavonol benzyl ether (XCII) through the corresponding flavanone, 3-nitroflavancne, and flavanol. The benzyl ether (XCII) on reduction gave the catechin (XCIII) which could be first isolated in a crystalline form as its acetate. On hydrolysing the latter, ($\pm$)-afzelechin trimethyl ether¹⁰² (XCIII) could be synthesised.

(LXXXVII)
7,3',4'-Trimethoxyflavonol benzyl ether.

(LXXXVIII)
trans-7,3',4'-Trimethoxy-3-benzyloxyflavan.

* H and OCH₂Ph (e) linkings will be on simple lines and not in dotted lines as shown.

In conclusion, it may be stated that the above work represents the first systematic investigations on the synthesis and stereochemistry for leucoanthocyanidins and the related compounds. The primary object of the synthesis of all the four racemates of a leucoanthocyanidin was realised. For the first time, Barton's concept of conformational analysis was introduced in this field and the stereochemistry of leucoanthocyanidins and related compounds was placed on a firm footing. Incidentally, both the synthetic and the natural dihydroflavonols were assigned stereochemical configurations, which have been confirmed later by several investigators. With the judicious use of metal hydrides and other hydrogenating catalysts, several naturally occurring compounds, such as, fustin trimethyl ether, dihydrorobinetin tetramethyl ether, guibourtacacidin dimethyl ether, leucorobinetidin tetramethyl ether, and mollisacacidin were synthesised. A new method was developed for the synthesis of catechins and synthesis of (±)-fisetinidol trimethyl ether, (±)-robinetinidol tetramethyl ether and (±)-afzechin trimethyl ether was accomplished.

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* H and (e) linkings will be in simple lines and not in dotted lines as shown.

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